

D5.3 Stakeholder and industry representative engagement

Date of deliverable:

31/05/2024

Responsible partner:

OASC

Author(s):

Alex Guhak (OASC), Niccolò Fattirolli and Laura Luna Moreno Morales (olivoENERGY)

Technical References

EU Initiative Call	CEF-DIG-2022-TA CEF Project Grants
Granting Authority	European Health and Digital Executive Agency
Grant Agreement Nr.	101133306
Project Acronym	22-EU-DIG-BEGONIA
Project Name	Enabling the Internet of Energy and Optimized Transport through Cross-Border Digital Platforms
Project Coordinator	Danmarks Tekniske Universitet
Project Duration	27 months

Deliverable No.	5.3
Dissemination level ¹	PU
Work Package	5
Task	5.1
Lead beneficiary	OASC
Responsible Authors	Alex Gluhak, Niccolò Fattirolli, Laura Luna Moreno Morales
Other authors/contributors	N/A
Contributing beneficiary(ies)	<i>olivoENERGY</i>
Due date of deliverable	31/05/2024
Actual submission date	31/05/2024

¹ PU = Public

PP = Restricted to other programme participants (including the Commission Services)

RE = Restricted to a group specified by the consortium (including the Commission Services)

CO = Confidential, only for members of the consortium (including the Commission Services)

Review

Reviewers	Razgar Ebrahimy, Mohsen Banaei
Reviewing period	20/05/2024 - 24/05/2024
Approved by reviewers	Razgar Ebrahimy - 30/05/2024

Document history

Issue	Date	Author	Content and changes
V0.1	14/04/2024	Alex Gluhak	Index, outline of the main contents
V0.2	18/04/2024	Niccolo Fattirolli	Frist draft section 1.1 and 1.2
V0.3	30/04/2024	Alex Gluhak	Updates to section 1 First draft of section 2 and 3
V0.4	10/05/2024	Niccolo Fattirolli	Inputs and second draft of sections 2 and 3
V0.5	19/05/2024	Alex Gluhak	Finalisation
V0.9	24/05/2024	Alex Gluhak, Laura Moreno Morales	Addressing of internal review comments, small additions to the text
V1.0	29/05/2024	Alex Gluhak	

Summary

BEGONIA Project

Europe is embarking on a transformative endeavour to modernise digital information usage, with a focus on enhancing the efficiency, sustainability, and connectivity of our energy and transportation sectors. At the core of this initiative lies the development of advanced Operational Digital Platforms (ODPs) that transcend national boundaries, leveraging state-of-the-art technologies such as data sharing, cloud computing, and network connectivity.

The BEGONIA Project is an EU-funded Coordination and Support Action that aims to expedite this digital transformation in the energy and transport sectors, analysing the most promising solutions and providing information to the European Commission to set up and fund future works project(s).

BEGONIA has the goal of identifying, studying and preparing the development of Operational Digital Platforms (ODPs) across different EU countries, starting from the identification of 10 cross-border and possibly cross-sector (energy and transport) use cases, meticulously shortlisting three based on predefined criteria, and evaluating their impacts through proof-of-concept implementation of their ODPs.

Summary of the Deliverable

To support different work streams of the project, this document presents a stakeholder engagement plan for the BEGONIA project. It identifies three target groups of stakeholders essential to the project:

- 1) Key experts, associations, and organisations to act as a continuous sounding board for BEGONIA and provide access to missing expertise or identified gaps in the project.
- 2) Project followers from the wider R&D and policy community who are interested in the project outcomes or seek active collaboration.
- 3) Partners of a potential ODP implementation project that the BEGONIA action is preparing.

The document describes a suitable engagement strategy for each of these target groups.

For the engagement of experts and advisors (target group 1) short-term and longer-term strategies have been developed, which take into account the project's prioritised engagement needs at different stages of the project and suitable engagement tools.

D5.3 Stakeholders and industry representative engagement

For the followers of the project (target group 2) a communication and dissemination plan is sketched out identifying adequate dissemination channels and the communication strategy of the project.

To address the needs of potential ODP implementation partners (target group 3) the project outlines a knowledge transfer strategy that ensures that all relevant learnings from the preparatory action are effectively transferred to maximise the initial investment made by the EC.

Disclaimer

Funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or HADEA. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

Table of Contents

Technical References.....	1
Review.....	2
Document history.....	3
Summary.....	4
BEGONIA Project.....	4
Summary of the Deliverable.....	4
Table of Acronyms.....	7
List of Figures.....	8
List of Tables.....	8
1. Introduction.....	9
1.1. Begonia Project.....	9
1.2. Work Package 5.....	9
1.3. Task 5.1 and deliverable D5.2 scope.....	9
2. Stakeholder engagement strategy.....	11
2.1. The purpose of stakeholder engagement in BEGONIA.....	11
2.2. Identification of relevant stakeholders.....	13
2.3. Engagement of experts and advisors.....	14
2.3.1. Shorter term engagement.....	16
2.3.2. Longer-term stakeholder engagement.....	17
2.4. Engagement of project followers and communication strategies.....	20
Objectives.....	21
3. Knowledge transfer strategy.....	24
3.1. Purpose of knowledge transfer in BEGONIA.....	24
3.2. Knowledge transfer mechanisms.....	24
4. Conclusion.....	26

Table of Acronyms

Acronyms	Description
CA	Consortium Agreement
EC	European Commission
EU	European Union
ODPs	Operational Digital Platforms
T5.1	Task 5.1
WP(s)	Work Package(s)

List of Figures

Figure 1: Groups of stakeholders BEGONIA will be engaging with.	11
Figure 2: Approached stakeholder list.	15
Figure 3: Stakeholder Engagement GANTT (General and Short-term Tasks). M2: February 2024.	17
Figure 4: Stakeholder engagement platform.	18
Figure 5: Stakeholder Engagement GANTT (Long-term strategy). M5: May 2024.	20

List of Tables

Table 1: Identified stakeholders	14
Table 2: Stakeholder engagement activities.....	18
Table 3: Dissemination activities	22

1. Introduction

1.1. Begonia Project

The BEGONIA Project aims to expedite the European digital transformation by analysing promising solutions emerging on the market and by providing recommendations to the European Commission (EC). Specifically, the project focuses on identifying, studying, and preparing the development of Operational Digital Platforms (ODPs) in the energy and transport sectors across various EU countries, to facilitate the setup and funding of future projects.

1.2. Work Package 5

Work Package (WP) 5 *“Stakeholders' engagement, Dissemination and Knowledge transfer”* runs throughout the 27 months of the project and interacts with all other WPs with multiple objectives.

Firstly, WP5 plans and carries out the Communication and Dissemination of Begonia. Communication and Dissemination encompasses the definition of the project's visual identity to support the internal and external dissemination activities, and the implementation of a series of actions that will facilitate the engagement of the community of experts, including a web platform.

Secondly, WP5 has the goal of creating a community of stakeholders to gather valuable market inputs and feedback, find partners, and provide other WPs with appropriate market information and expert insights where necessary. To this end, WP5 actively engages experts, industry representatives, and relevant stakeholders in a value-added community for the project.

Finally, WP5 will carry out a know-how transfer of the projects' conclusions to the European Commission for the definition of the new calls for project(s) and, in the final months of the project, to the entities awarded the new project(s), providing information and support in the initial phases.

1.3. Task 5.1 and deliverable D5.3 scope

This deliverable presents the results of activities that have been carried out in the context of a broader Task, namely Task 5.1 (T5.1).

This task has the purpose of setting up the work for all other WP5 tasks setting up relevant communities, engagement plans and tools to successfully carry out the envisioned WP5 work.

T5.1 has several objectives that are developed in parallel in close synchronisation to ensure consistency:

1. To define and implement the project Visual Identity.
2. To draft the project Communication and Dissemination plan.
3. To design and set up the project website and a platform to facilitate the stakeholders' engagement and knowledge transfer.
4. To identify the most relevant stakeholders to be involved.
5. To define a strategy to approach stakeholders to be included in a community to engage with throughout the project, both to provide feedback and inputs to all work packages and allow more transparency.
6. To define a strategy to facilitate the know-how transfer of the project conclusions.

This deliverable focuses on items 4-6 of this task. It provides a stakeholder engagement strategy of how to engage the most relevant stakeholders as part of the project, including Industry representatives and associations.

It identifies relevant stakeholder groups and defines a toolbox for engagement that will consist of a combination of digital tools and in-person and virtual events according to expected project needs.

The document also identifies strategic considerations for the knowledge transfer of BEGONIA to the EC and other organisations that will engage in a later implementation phase of identified use cases.

2. Stakeholder engagement strategy

2.1. The purpose of stakeholder engagement in BEGONIA

The goal of the BEGONIA project is to identify and prepare use cases for the deployment of cross-border cross-sector operational digital platforms, conduct feasibility studies, and establish regulatory and technical frameworks for each selected use case from at least 7 EU Member States. The digital platforms will incorporate renewable energy sources, enhance energy production and consumption efficiency, encourage the adoption of eco-friendly transportation modes, and minimize carbon emissions, thereby supporting the EU's environmental and energy objectives.

While BEGONIA brings together a strong consortium of partners with relevant expertise in digital platforms, energy and transport from five EU member states (Denmark, Spain, Austria, Belgium and Greece), there is a need for the project to engage with a wider range of stakeholders in Europe to get access to further complementary expertise, capture a broader range of ideas and inputs and forge synergies with ongoing European initiatives on the ground.

There are several external stakeholders that the BEGONIA project envisions to engage with it. They can be broadly grouped into three categories as shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1: Groups of stakeholders BEGONIA will be engaging with.

The first stakeholder group brings together key experts, associations, and organisations to act as a continuous sounding board for BEGONIA and provide access to missing expertise or identified gaps in the project.

The second stakeholder group consists of followers of our project activities which are organically grown through our dissemination and communication activities.

The third group of stakeholders is to be created through an EC tender process. It will contain partners of the winning consortium who have been selected for the

implementation of the ODP, whose specifications the BEGONIA project is preparing. Stakeholder interaction with this stakeholder group is more unidirectional in terms of value flow and primarily focused on knowledge transfer from the BEGONIA project as contractually agreed. This contrasts with the interactions with the two stakeholder groups where the engagements provide clear mutual benefits to the project.

In the following, we briefly expand on each of these in more detail.

Group1: Experts and advisory board

External experts and advisory boards will be engaged to support the BEGONIA project with the needs of various project activities. Some of this engagement is required to seek specific input for key milestones /deliverables of the project, in other cases it is to provide ad-hoc advice and access to expertise whenever needs emerge. External experts and advisory boards aim to contribute complementary know-how and regulatory, technical and market insights to the project.

More specifically in WP2, BEGONIA is seeking suitable use case ideas and feedback on identified use cases to ensure that our project considers the most relevant ones for analysis and selects the most promising ones to be recommended for further implementation through feasibility studies in the project.

In WP3, BEGONIA requires further input on architecture, regulatory advice, and governance to successfully conduct the feasibility studies and to further improve the technical specifications based on validated learnings.

In WP4, BEGONIA requires further advice on the preparation of procurement templates and framework agreements for the subsequent implementation of the studied open digital platform. Stakeholders could also support the activation of a wide market to respond to any resulting upcoming EC tenders from this action.

Section 2.2 defines a range of relevant stakeholder categories that the project identified for further engagement.

We describe an appropriate short-term engagement plan that accommodates early-stage project needs in section 2.3.1 For other project activities, a more holistic longer-term stakeholder engagement approach has been developed, to take full advantage of different engagement tools available for the project. Further details on this are provided in section 2.3.2.

Group2: Followers of the BEGONIA project

BEGONIA aims to communicate project progress and achievements to a wider research and innovation community in the areas of digital technology, energy and transport and

corresponding policymakers. By establishing a web and social media presence for the project we expect an organic growth of project followers who engage with our content in the form of workshops, posts, articles and updates provided on the website and LinkedIn page and through an e-mail newsletter. This engagement can ensure that 1) knowledge created in the BEGONIA project can provide benefits to other individuals, organisations and initiatives and that 2) opportunities emerge for collaboration to forge further synergies with existing initiatives and organisations.

It is possible that stakeholders initially engaged as followers could also take a more active role by becoming expert advisors to the project (Group1) or become successful bidders in the future tender for the implementation of the recommended ODP use cases and specifications (Group 3).

Group3: ODP implementation project partners

BEGONIA aims to prepare the required technical specifications for an ODP implementation project that the EC is likely to put out for tender to the market. In case such action goes ahead, BEGONIA will engage with the partners of the winning consortium to provide a smooth transition of knowledge and know-how developed in the project to support them in the implementation phase and thus improve their chances of success. Details on the planned knowledge transfer activities are provided in Section 3.

2.2. Identification of relevant stakeholders

The establishment of the first stakeholder group requires a proactive engagement approach of BEGONIA. Stakeholder groups 2 and 3 are more organically grown due to project dissemination and communication activities or the subsequent tendering process run by the EC. Therefore, we focus stakeholder identification primarily on the first group.

The required knowledge exchange with external stakeholders requires a broad range of stakeholders that the project can lean on for input and expertise.

Our goal is to build a stakeholder group of experts and advisors that provides a balanced view across all relevant stakeholder categories involving organisations across different parts of Europe.

The first step has been to identify suitable stakeholders and to approach them directly for engagement.

The table below shows the different categories that BEGONIA has identified including examples in the networks of the consortium partners that will be targeted for engagement.

Stakeholder category	Example stakeholders
EU projects	Int:Net, OMEGA-X, ENERSHARE, Data Cellar, EDDIE Synergies, CETP, Green.Dat.AI, Wataverse, Open Continuum, Mobi Spaces, TRUSTEE, TANGO, TEADAL, GLACIATON, Twin EU, Interconnect, Unlock-CEI , ODEON, HEDGE-IoT, ELEXIA
EU initiatives	EiT InnoEnergy, ETIP.SNET, BRIDGE Data management WG Clean Energy transition partnership, European Digital Infrastructure Consortium (EDIC), DS4SSCC
Associations	smarten, AIOTI, OpenADR Alliance, Gaia-X Data space business alliance, AVERE, CHAdEMO, Mobility Portal Europe, APPLiA, Green Power Denmark, AISCAT Servizi, UIC, FEHRL, ALICE, IWT, ECTP
Institutional and Regulatory bodies or experts	ACER, Florence School of Regulation, E.DSO, ENTSO-E, Danish Energy Agency, Agency for Digital Government, SDFI, Spanish Transport Ministry, Cabildo de Tenerife (Canary Islands)
National Research Centres	Energy systems Catapult, CEA, Vito , Fraunhofer Energy Alliance, Alexandra Institute, CARTIF, ITG, CIRCE, CIMNE, TECNALIA, TEKNIKER
Companies	KONSTANT, True Energy, Spirii, Nuvve, EWII/Monta, EVN, Acciona, Grupo Cuerva, Estabanell
DSO/TSO	TREFOR, Energinet, Energie Steiermark

Table 1: Identified stakeholders

2.3. Engagement of experts and advisors

This section provides an overview of the proposed engagement plan for experts and advisors that the project requires. We split the engagement plan into two parts based on timings. Due to the immediate needs of WP2, the project took a pragmatic approach to reach out to relevant stakeholders, while engagement tools such as the stakeholder engagement platform are being developed. Although in the early stages, the focus was on supporting the short-term needs of the project, the actions taken, including the identification of stakeholders, were developed to serve as the basis for the entire engagement strategy established for the project.

With the support of all BEGONIA members, a comprehensive stakeholder list was drawn up for an initial assessment of the most appropriate entities to be involved in the short-term and long-term phases of the project. A list of stakeholders that have already been contacted to ask for involvement in the project is shown in the figure below.

KIND	NAME OF STAKEHOLDER	PURPOSE OF APPROACH			AREA OF FOCUS/EXPERTISE E.g. Energy, Transport, Regulation, Grids,
		CASES PROVIDED	CASES REVIEW	LONG TERM INVOLVEMENT	
EU Projects	Int:Net		X	X	Energy Data Spaces
	OMEGA-X	X	X		Energy Data Spaces
	EDDIE	X	X	X	Energy Data Spaces
	ELEXIA		X	X	Energy Data Spaces
EU Initiatives	ETIP.SNET	X	X		Energy, Regulation, Grids
	DS4SSCC	X	X	X	Energy, Data
Associations	smartEn		X	X	Energy, Grids, Transport, Regulation
	AIOTI	?	X	X	
	ILWT	X	X		Inland Waterway Association
	ECTP	X	X	X	EU Construction Technology Platform
Institutional and Regulatory bodies or experts	Florence School of Regulation	?	X		Regulation, Energy, Transport, Grids
	E.DSO		X	X	Grids, Energy, Regulation
	ENTSO-E		X		Grids, Energy, Regulation
	Danish Energy Agency		X	X	Data Spaces
	Directorate-General for Roads (Transport Ministry of Spain)	X	X	X	Road management, maintenance and planning
	Cabildo de Tenerife (Canary Islands)	X		X	Traffic Management
	Cabildo de La Gomera (Canary Islands)			X	Traffic Management
	Valencia Port (Spain)			X	Port and logistic management
	Costanza Port (Romania)			X	Port and logistic management (inland waterways)
	Klaipedia Port (Lithuania)				Port and logistic management
	Infraestruturas de Portugal			X	Road and Railways management, maintenance and planning
	Brujas-Amberes Port				Port and logistic management (inland waterways)
	Puerto de Sevilla (Spain)		X	X	Port and logistic management (inland waterways)
	Puerto de Vigo (Spain)		X	X	Port and logistic management
National Research Centres	Energy systems Catapult (UK)	X	X		
	Vito (BE)	X	X		
	CARTIF			X	Smart grids and buildings
	University of Málaga			X	Data Spaces
Companies	KONSTANT		X		Grids
	EWIII/Monta	X	X	X	EVs
	EVN	X	X	X	Grids, EVs
	Acciona		X	X	
	AISCAT Servizi		X		
DSO/TSO	TREFOR	X	X	X	Grids
	Energinet	X	X	X	Data Spaces
	Energie Steiermark	X	X	X	Grids, EVs

Figure 2: Approached stakeholder list.

More details on this two-phase approach can be found in the following sections.

2.3.1. Shorter term engagement

The use case identification in WP2 required the engagement of stakeholders at the early stages of the project. This was mainly driven by the need for input to an early deliverable D2.1 “Preliminary collection of operational digital platforms for energy and transport cross-borders in EU”, which was due already in M5 of the project.

The stakeholder engagement focused on the curation and development of at least 10 promising candidate high-level use cases, to be considered later in the project for more detailed evaluation.

The use case ideas should be motivated by the real needs of stakeholders in the respective sector value chains. They should be ideally cross-border, cross-sector in nature and be representative of the sector/industry as such, not only relevant for individual organisations.

A second related engagement need relates to the appraisal of the identified use cases by industry experts so their feedback can be used to further improve the use cases before a more detailed analysis and selection of the use cases are performed.

To respond to these short-term needs within adequate timelines, we decided to take a 2-pronged approach to the development of our stakeholder engagement strategy.

After performing an initial stakeholder mapping and identification, we developed a pragmatic short-term engagement strategy to ensure the timely sourcing of use cases for WP2 and the recruitment of an initial group of expert stakeholders to act as an advisory panel for the use cases. In parallel, we also developed a longer-term strategy for stakeholder engagement, which is described in the next section.

The short-term engagement approach required all project partners to reach out to their respective networks to solicit contributions to use cases and/or to identify willing experts to act in our use case advisory panel.

For this purpose, we developed a narrative document and corresponding presentation slides that each project partner could use to present the project and its ambitions and explain to external stakeholders the nature of expected contributions, project processes and timelines. As we had no money allocated to compensate external participants in this process, we also needed to develop a suitable narrative to explain the value of getting engaged with us and contributing in kind to our activities.

Each project partner could then rely on the narrative and common approach to work their network to solicit use cases and identify suitable experts for the use case advisory board.

The picture below shows the timeline for early-stage engagement activities.

	TASKS	IN CHARGE PARTICIPATING		TIMELINE AND DEADLINES																			
				M2				M3				M4				M5				M6			
				W1	W2	W3	W4	W1	W2	W3	W4	W1	W2	W3	W4	W1	W2	W3	W4	W1	W2	W3	W4
General Tasks	Preparation of the Narrative documents	OLIVO/OASC																					
	Preparation of the Stakeholders list and filtering	OLIVO/OASC	ALL																				
Short-term Tasks	Contact stakeholders for new use-cases gathering (Use-cases providers)	ALL																					
	Contact stakeholders to create an expert group (Use-cases reviewers)	ALL																					
	Clustering of reviewers and briefing (KOC)	OLIVO/OASC	ALL																				
	Set up and launch project platform	OLIVO/OASC																					
	Reviewers feedback of use-cases	OLIVO/OASC	CEMOSA/DTU																				

Figure 3: Stakeholder Engagement GANTT (General and Short-term Tasks). M2: February 2024.

Use case gathering needed to be completed by mid-April 24. This was achieved by targeting a subset of the initially identified stakeholders that are likely able to deliver use cases against the short deadlines.

The stakeholder group of experts for the use case advisory board needed to be in place by mid-May 24. The second part of May 24 was used to allocate use cases to experts matching their backgrounds and areas of expertise according to the scope of the use case. Use case evaluation and feedback are expected to take place throughout June and July 24 using the project platform. The project platform (core of the long-term stakeholder engagement, depicted in purple in the GANTT above) will be set up by M5 (end of May 2024) to facilitate the work even in this first phase.

Experts who are willing to support the project beyond the use case advisory work will be retained in a stakeholder group for the longer-term engagement of the project.

2.3.2. Longer-term stakeholder engagement

Our longer-term stakeholder engagement strategy considers all other project needs beyond the short-term needs of WP2. While our short-term strategy relied primarily on direct engagements with stakeholders in our immediate network, the longer-term strategy makes use of the stakeholder engagement platform as an essential tool, as described in deliverable D5.2 Platform Guidance Document.

Figure 4 shows the features of the engagement platforms that we would like to leverage to engage with our expert and advisory stakeholders more effectively.

Figure 4: Stakeholder engagement platform.

The need for occasional bilateral conversation will remain, where very specific advice or input is required. However, we will also use platform features to host roundtable meetings and discussion channels on specific topics, send out survey forms and questionnaires and exchange information through a document repository. Activities that will be carried out thanks to the platform tools that will be utilized to facilitate engagement are the following, complementing and overlapping the more generalist dissemination activities.

Table 2: Stakeholder engagement activities

Engagement tool	Purpose	Details / Content / Frequency
Newsfeed	Provide regular progress updates with more detail than social media posts or website	Use of the Newsfeed tool on the project platform to share updates (monthly) on the progress and developments of the project to update involved stakeholders and keeping them engaged in the project. Newsfeed might also be connected to the website and shared with a wider audience.
Discussion groups on engagement platform and questionnaires	Solicit input from the stakeholders' community on specific topics, share documents and allow parallel work to provide feedback	<p>Topic dependent, created on demand for specific WPs or Deliverables.</p> <p>Questionnaires will be sent using Microsoft Forms -both during the discussions and before or after- to facilitate the collection of experts' opinions.</p> <p>Documents will be shared in dedicated channels/shared folders to gather feedback.</p> <p>First interactions scheduled for June 2024.</p>

		Other interactions will be planned according to the project development and WP needs.
EU concertation meetings	Share knowledge with other relevant EU initiatives or associations and align approaches, facilitation of contact with relevant stakeholders	Virtual (or where possible in-person) meetings to share key project outcomes and findings and strengthen synergies with other European initiatives or associations in the data, energy and transport sectors. Examples are: the BRIGDE initiative, ETIP SNET, the Int:Net project, the association smarten, E-DSO, etc..
Webinars or virtual events	Dissemination of project findings and facilitation of contact with relevant stakeholders	Virtual events will be organized on the project platform to share key outcomes and findings. Webinar and virtual events are planned for the end of the main WPs, namely in M11, in M18 and in M27 (in conjunction with the final event of the project). This activity will follow the project evolution and needs so it may be subject to changes. It overlaps with the general dissemination activities.

Furthermore, the stakeholder engagement platform not only serves as a platform to serve the requirements of BEGONIA but will support easier peer-to-peer exchange between experts and advisors. This community dimension will provide further incentives for stakeholders to participate and network with each other.

The initial group of experts and advisors who supported us with the use case work for WP2 will be enhanced with additional experts and advisors depending on the needs of the other work packages.

In order to involve an ever-widening community of experts, the involvement strategy will run throughout the duration of the project, at least until M18, when the recommendation will be sent to the European Commission. Coordination and collection of input from the stakeholder community will then continue until the end of the project.

Once the project platform is created and launched, the focus will be on the short-term needs described above and engagement with use case reviewers. However, in parallel,

all entities selected in the early stages of the engagement activity will be contacted and invited to participate in the platform (M6-M7). Subsequently, a coordination meeting with BEGONIA members - which will take place virtually or in the context of a physical meeting of the consortium - will allow aligning the project needs due to the start-up of WP3 and the identification of new potentially interesting stakeholder profiles to be invited to join BEGONIA (M7). In this case, a new round of stakeholder identification and invitation will be launched and finalised in the last stages of WP2 (M10). The same pattern will be repeated at the beginning of WP4 (M13).

This timeline should be regarded as indicative, as activities may be adapted to and react to sudden project needs, and as general engagement with relevant stakeholders will be conducted throughout the duration of the project, also facilitated by dissemination activities.

	TASKS	IN CHARGE PARTICIPATING		TIMELINE AND DEADLINES															
				M5	M6	M7	M8	M9	M10	M11	M12	M13	M14	M15	M16	M17	M18	M19-M27	
Long-term Tasks	Set up and launch project platform	OLIVO/OASC																	
	Contact other identified stakeholders to expand the community	ALL																	
	Internal reassessment of the project needs (WP3/WP4)	OLIVO/OASC	ALL																
	New round of stakeholders identification and invitation (if deemed necessary)	ALL																	
	Inclusion of interested Stakeholders engaged through dissemination activities and the project platform	ALL																	

Figure 5: Stakeholder Engagement GANTT (Long-term strategy). M5: May 2024.

2.4. Engagement of project followers and communication strategies

The main purpose of engaging with this stakeholder group is to inform the wider community in Europe about the progress of the project and to provide opportunities to gather additional input and forge synergies with existing initiatives.

The engagement of a wider audience is a broader activity that targets both experienced stakeholders and an industry but more general public. It falls within the scope of the general communication and dissemination of the project for which a dedicated Plan has been developed.

One of the purposes of the communication and dissemination is also attracting experts and other parties that are not proactively approached by project partners but that might still be interested in following the developments of BEGONIA and participating by sharing their expertise or opinion.

The aforementioned communication and dissemination Plan has been developed since the beginning of the project and is summarized below.

Objectives

- Make Begonia a reference project at the EU level.
- Engage with relevant stakeholders and increase cooperation efforts.
- Raise awareness on the relevance of the topics treated and foster discussions and exchange of information between stakeholders.

Key messaging

The register will be tailored to the target audience and will be differentiated depending on the context. Events or webinars organized for an interaction with the Community will be more technical and in-depth, as will the communication with the new works projects. On the other hand, the social media activity and the publication of leaflets and brochures, destined for a wider audience, will be clear, concise, and easy to understand for all kinds of readers, even if always aligned with the values and goals of the project.

Target audiences

The communication activity primarily targets high-level entities, companies, individual experts, politicians, and organizations at the European level involved in the energy, transport, and digitalization sectors. This encompasses members of European and national regulatory bodies (including the Commission), associations in the data, energy, and transport fields, suppliers, service providers, system operators, as well as other European research projects and initiatives.

While these profiles represent the primary audience for BEGONIA's communication and dissemination efforts, additional focus will be placed on engaging a broader audience interested in the study's outcomes. Communication towards this wider audience will be made simpler and clearer.

Communication channels and Activities

A variety of dissemination channels will be used to reach this audience. The table below provides an overview of the outreach channels considered, their purpose and nature of content for the engagement and expected communication frequency. As anticipated, some activities overlap with the long-term stakeholder engagement presented above.

Table 3: Dissemination activities

Dissemination channel	Purpose	Details / Content / Frequency
Website	<p>Communicate project objectives to the wider community.</p> <p>Attract stakeholders and provide access to more information</p>	<p>Overview of the project and partners (business card)</p> <p>Provide updates of main project outcomes (Deliverables and Use cases development) once finalized.</p> <p>Hub to access community engagement platform / document repositories.</p>
Social media	<p>Communicate project to the wider community.</p> <p>Provide regular progress updates.</p>	<p>Regular social media posts on LinkedIn and X (4 every month) are published to present general projects' developments and insights to update followers and keep their interest engaged in the project.</p>
Webinars or virtual events	<p>Dissemination of project findings and facilitation of contact with relevant stakeholders</p>	<p>Virtual events will be organized on the project platform to share key outcomes and findings.</p> <p>This activity will follow the project evolution and needs so it may be subject to changes.</p> <p>Webinar and virtual events are planned for the end of the main WPs, namely in M11, in M18 and in M27 (in conjunction with the final event of the project).</p>
In person events	<p>Dissemination of project findings and facilitation of contact with relevant stakeholders</p>	<p>EU events and trade fairs:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • BEGONIA plans to participate in 6 events either as attendance of project members or with booth and content presentation. • The events participation will be equally distributed during the project lifetime (4 between M1-M18 and 2 between M19-M27). • As of May 2024, BEGONIA participated to FEL2050 in April 2024 and has organized to take part in ENLIT 2024.

		<p>Independently organized events:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none">• BEGONIA will organize a closing event inviting the Commission, the winning consortium/a of the follow up project and all the stakeholders involved in the activities. Event is scheduled for M27. More physical events might be organized as needed.
--	--	---

3. Knowledge transfer strategy

3.1. Purpose of knowledge transfer in BEGONIA

BEGONIA is preparing the grounds for future implementation projects for cross-sector cross-border operational digital platforms. The outcomes of BEGONIA will directly influence the future funding tenders launched by the EC. In case the EC decides to proceed with such calls and selects (a) winning consortium/consortia, BEGONIA will facilitate the knowledge transfer towards these stakeholders (identified as stakeholder group3 in the previous section).

Such knowledge transfer activities are likely to be carried out during the last six months of the project and will ensure that the winning consortium/a will receive an easy access to all findings of BEGONIA and future recommendations, so they are well equipped for the successful delivery of an operational digital platform implementation.

3.2. Knowledge transfer mechanisms

The knowledge transfer to potentially winning consortium/consortia will be facilitated through a combined range of actions.

Access to documented knowledge and key contacts

A key role in the knowledge transfer plays the stakeholder engagement platform (see Figure 2), which will gather relevant project deliverables, documentation, previous stakeholder community discussions and relevant stakeholder contacts, acting as a knowledge and contact hub.

The contracted partners of any follow up implementation action will be onboarded to the platform and provided with access to all relevant information.

A comprehensive list of the long term stakeholders and stakeholder followers will be passed on to the winning consortium. The list will include contact details, area of expertise, etc so they can be reach to provide support along the winning project development and execution.

Knowledge transfer workshops

BEGONIA aims to organise two specific workshops to facilitate knowledge transfer:

- 1) **Onboarding workshop:** An introductory workshop early on that will present the concept, the initial conclusions, the know-how developed, and the documentation produced at that stage of the project.
- 2) **Handover workshop:** executed at the end of the BEGONIA project. It will be organized as the conclusion of Task 5.3, in which the general recommendations and guidelines will be presented.

Expert team engagement

BEGONIA will set up a dedicated team of project internal experts with the responsibility of holding bilateral meetings (virtual) with the members of the winning consortium/consortia of any follow-on implementation action. Together with these stakeholders, it will identify the other parties' specific personalised knowledge support needs and support the other projects' ramp-up activities, including potential updates to their work description, drawing upon BEGONIA's extensive experiences from the validation phases. It is envisioned that 2-3 bilateral meetings will be required between key representatives of the projects.

Moreover, coordination between the winning consortium/consortia and the activities of the final technical Work Package of the project -WP4- will be ensured through recurrent bilateral meetings. BEGONIA will continue to support these until the project ends.

Invitation to project events

The winning consortium/consortia will be invited to all events (virtual and in-person, including the BEGONIA final event), presentations and webinars, when these occur while the new consortium has commenced its activities.

4. Conclusion

A key need of the BEGONIA project is to tap into the expertise and experience of the wider market so that the project can maximise its impact potential and deliver the most relevant use cases for cross-border cross-sector operational digital platforms.

This deliverable outlines a plan to engage with relevant stakeholders and industry representatives to accomplish this goal. The chosen approach balances well the immediate and longer-term needs of the project and considers emerging requirements and evolving engagement needs of the project. This flexibility will allow the project to draw upon the most relevant expertise from the right stakeholders when needed and to consider continuous feedback from a rapidly changing market.

The document also outlines a plan for adequate knowledge transfer to future parties, who may be selected to implement digital operational platforms for Europe. This ensures that such parties can fully benefit from all learnings obtained in this preparatory action, thus maximising investment made by the European Commission.